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GRAPHIA

Knowledge Graphs, AI Services and Next Generation Instrumentation for R&D in Social Sciences and Humanities

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Project Coordination and Management

Deliverable D1.1
Data Management Plan

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CNRS	Centre national de la recherche scientifique
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
JUST	Judicious, Unbiased, Safe, Transparent
KG	Knowledge Graph
LLM	Large Language Model
LLM4SSH	Large Language Model for Social Sciences and Humanities
LPG	Labelled Property Graph
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SME	Subject-Matter Expert
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This Data Management Plan (DMP) defines the strategy for handling data generated and used throughout the lifecycle of the GRAPHIA project. The plan supports the project's overarching goals by ensuring the responsible, efficient and ethical management of various data types across all work packages.

The DMP defines the types of data to be collected and describes their expected formats, sources and volumes. It provides a framework for storing, sharing and preserving data according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles and prioritises open access and long-term usability where possible.

The document also defines a data management framework, specifying how responsibilities are distributed among project partners and how appropriate resources are allocated. In addition, the plan addresses data security by outlining general measures to protect information throughout its lifecycle. It defines expectations for secure storage, controlled access and responsible sharing of data, taking into account levels of sensitivity.

Ethical issues are an integral part of the DMP. The plan establishes principles to ensure that all data involving people is collected and processed responsibly, in full compliance with legal obligations and institutional ethical standards.

This DMP is a living document that will be revised as the project evolves, adapting to new types of data, emerging ethical issues and technological developments. It ensures that the data produced by GRAPHIA will make a significant contribution to future research, infrastructure development and open science.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This Data Management Plan has been developed as an integral part of the GRAPHIA scientific infrastructure initiative. The purpose of this document is to outline how data generated, collected, processed, and stored throughout the project lifecycle will be handled to ensure its quality, accessibility, interoperability, and long-term preservation.

Scientific infrastructure projects produce a wide array of datasets that are critical not only for the success of the project itself but also for the broader scientific community. Proper data management ensures that these valuable resources are made available in a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) manner, in line with international best practices and funder requirements.

All public datasets, documentation, and software outputs generated by GRAPHIA will acknowledge EU funding in accordance with Horizon Europe requirements and will include a reference to the Grant Agreement number. This ensures transparency and proper attribution of financial support.

The outputs of the project—such as LLM4SSH, the SSH Knowledge Graph, and AI-based modules—are designed to be usable and accessible by external researchers, SMEs, and other projects. Open standards and APIs will be implemented to maximise interoperability and reuse beyond the project's original scope.

This plan also addresses issues related to data provenance and governance, ensuring the traceability, accountability, and stewardship of data assets throughout their lifecycle. These aspects are closely aligned with activities under Task 5.1 and the development of the Data Trust Framework, which provides a comprehensive policy and technical foundation for trustworthy data sharing.

Intellectual Property generated during the project will be managed in compliance with the Consortium Agreement and relevant EU regulations. This includes the proper attribution, licensing, and exploitation of results to support both academic and commercial uptake.

Furthermore, the use of AI technologies in GRAPHIA will comply with emerging European regulatory frameworks, including the EU AI Act¹. Ethical considerations, transparency, and risk management will be embedded in all AI-related processes to ensure responsible innovation.

The plan will be continuously reviewed and updated as the project evolves, ensuring that it remains aligned with the project's objectives, technological developments, and institutional policies.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This DMP addresses the following key areas:

1. A summary of the types of data that will be produced and used within the project (chapter 2).
2. Strategies to ensure that data adheres to FAIR principles (chapter 3).
3. Allocation of responsibilities and resources related to data management (chapter 4).
4. Measures to ensure data security and confidentiality (chapter 5).
5. Considerations related to ethical and legal compliance (chapter 6).

¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (AI Act). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>

2. Data summary

The GRAPHIA project generates a wide range of data types reflecting its interdisciplinary, collaborative and infrastructure-focused nature. This section provides a structured overview of the nature, origin, purpose, and intended processing of the key datasets generated throughout the project lifecycle. Details about comprehensive description are available in Appendix A (GRAPHIA Data Identification Table).

2.1 Overview of data types and purposes

GRAPHIA data can be grouped into the following categories:

- **Administrative and project management data**
Includes deliverables, milestones, financial reports, meeting notes, mailing lists and internal communication materials. These datasets mainly come from WP1 (Tasks 1.1-1.3) and support project coordination and reporting.
- **SSH Knowledge Graph data**
The SSH Knowledge Graph (SSH KG) comprises semantically structured datasets that represent research instruments, concepts, institutions, and communities in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). It is developed using a hybrid architecture that combines Resource Description Framework (RDF) and Labelled Property Graph (LPG) technologies, enabling both semantic reasoning and advanced graph analytics.

The SSH KG integrates standard ontologies and interoperable data models to ensure reusability across platforms and domains. It supports complex use cases involving artificial intelligence and large language models (LLMs), including automated enrichment, reasoning, and entity disambiguation.

Data used to populate the SSH KG originates from a range of curated sources, as outlined in the Grant Agreement. These include scientific publications, research project records, archival metadata, primary source documents, expert interviews, and scholarly articles. This reused data will be processed in accordance with applicable licenses and data governance policies, ensuring compliance and traceability.

A clear distinction is maintained between:

Input data: existing external datasets that are integrated into the KG;

Core knowledge structures: the SSH KG itself, including the schema, vocabularies, and enriched linkages we develop;

Derived data and metadata: outputs generated through enrichment pipelines, LLM-based inference, or AI modules.

Public-facing components of the SSH KG—including portions of the graph, documentation, APIs, and selected derived metadata—will be made openly accessible where licensing and privacy conditions allow. This ensures their usability for external researchers, cultural heritage institutions, SMEs, and related initiatives. More sensitive or restricted data may be available under controlled access agreements.

Ongoing work within the Data Trust Framework (Task 5.1) will further define the governance, sharing policies, and trust mechanisms that underpin the SSH KG and its associated outputs.

- **SSH LLMs and datasets for training/benchmarking**

The GRAPHIA project will create and curate domain-specific text datasets and training corpora for the development and evaluation of large language models (LLMs) tailored for SSH research. These datasets may include curated corpora, document collections, prompts, evaluation scripts and gold-standard annotations for benchmarking model performance. Depending on licensing and ethical restrictions, portions of these datasets may be made available for reuse or shared through controlled access mechanisms. The resulting models and evaluation results will contribute to the evidence-based development of AI services tailored to the research infrastructure in the SSH domain.

- **Ontological and semantic data**

Developed as part of WP2, specifically Task 2.1, these include controlled vocabularies, taxonomies and formal ontologies describing data, instrumentation and research processes in the social sciences and humanities (SSH). These datasets are intended to be published in open access on platforms such as GitLab and are compliant with FAIR and Semantic Web

standards.

- **Qualitative research data**

Includes interview recordings, transcriptions and thematic codes from co-design sessions with stakeholders and researchers. These are generated as part of WP5 (Tasks 5.2-5.3) to inform user needs analysis and evaluation of next-generation tools.

- **Workshops and event outputs**

Data collected during workshops and participatory events—such as videos, photos, Miro boards and collaborative artifacts—used for internal reflection, reporting and dissemination.

- **Survey and feedback data**

Includes quantitative and semi-structured responses collected through tools such as Mentimeter, Slido and online forms. Supports user evaluation, needs prioritisation and iterative tool development.

- **Software components files**

Includes source code and documentation of any software components, APIs or processing pipelines developed as part of the project. These are managed in repositories with version control (e.g., GitLab).

2.2 Data formats

Data are stored in a variety of interoperable and widely supported formats, including:

- **Text and documentation:** TXT, PDF, DOCX, ODT, GDOC
- **Spreadsheets and structured data:** CSV, XLSX, ODS, GSHEET, Parquet
- **Multimedia:** MP4 (video), JPEG/PNG (images), WAV/MP3 (audio)
- **Semantic and metadata formats:** JSON, JSON-LD, XML, TEI/XML, RDF/OWL
- **Software/code:** Source files in several programming languages, including Python, Java, JavaScript, etc. as applicable
- **Collaborative outputs:** Miro boards (exported as PDF or image)

These formats were selected to ensure long-term accessibility, interoperability, and reuse.

2.3 Estimated data volume

While exact volumes will evolve over time and many data items are not known at this stage of work, the following estimates illustrate typical expectations:

Data Type	Estimated Volume
Interview recordings and transcripts	Up to 5 GB
Workshop media and collaborative boards	Approx. 2 GB
Survey data	Up to 20 MB per iteration
Ontological artefacts	~10–20 MB
Administrative files	Numerous, but small individually
Source code repositories	Variable, up to 500 MB
Datasets for training/benchmarking the SSH LLMs	Potentially large
SSH Knowledge Graph data	Several TB

2.4 Data collection and handling

Data in GRAPHIA is collected through a combination of manual, semi-automated and AI-assisted processes, depending on the type of data and task. Most of the data is generated within the consortium through research activities such as interviews, co-design workshops, stakeholder events and tool evaluations. Additional data comes from selected external sources—such as academic publications, project records or archival metadata—which are reused under appropriate licenses and documented governance.

The project supports a wide range of data types, including text corpora, knowledge graph data, ontologies, survey responses, audiovisual workshop results, LLM training datasets and source code. Data collection methods vary: qualitative data (e.g., interviews, workshops) are collected using informed consent procedures; feedback

data are collected using digital tools (e.g., Mentimeter, Slido); and knowledge graph content is enriched using pipelines involving artificial intelligence-based extraction and inference modules.

All data collection processes comply with ethical protocols and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), including informed consent, data minimisation, anonymisation and limited access. Where artificial intelligence tools are involved in data enrichment or inference, results are subject to human oversight and traceability standards.

Data administrators and task leaders are responsible for ensuring documentation, metadata creation and validation at the point of data collection. Version control and secure storage mechanisms have been implemented to maintain the integrity and provenance of both raw and processed datasets.

2.5 Access, storage, and sharing

Data will be securely stored in the project's Google Workspace service, with access rights managed and verified by WPI. Public datasets, including ontologies and selected documentation, will be published in trusted open repositories, such as Zenodo, with appropriate metadata and open licenses (e.g., CC BY), ensuring long-term availability after the project is completed.

Decisions regarding public dissemination and access to restricted data are made by work package leaders in consultation with WPI and in accordance with guidelines developed under Task 5.1. These guidelines provide rules for data governance and ethical use, including procedures for requesting access to sensitive or non-open data sets and model agreements for both data providers and users.

Data will be deposited in accordance with FAIR principles and as required by Horizon Europe. Open access will be provided according to the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary,” and any restrictions on openness will be documented and justified in the DMP.

To support long-term preservation, all research results—including data, documentation and software—will be stored in repositories with persistent identifiers

(e.g., DOI). Zenodo and similar repositories provide persistent access and traceability, even after the project ends.

3. FAIR data

The GRAPHIA project adopts the FAIR principles to ensure data are managed to maximise accessibility and reuse. GRAPHIA is built on Open Science criteria. To succeed in its ambitions, the project will adopt different types of open science practices that are appropriate for the project.

- **Findable:** Each dataset is accompanied by metadata specifying the data type, origin (WP and Task), author or responsible partner, and usage constraints. Metadata will be compiled into an internal project data catalogue. For example, deliverables (e.g., D1.2, D1.3) and the GRAPHIA Ontology (D2.1) include clearly documented authorship and project context. Where appropriate, persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) will be assigned—particularly for public datasets hosted on Zenodo.
- **Accessible:** Internal data, including email addresses and financial spreadsheets (T1.1, T1.2), are securely stored on the project's Google Drive, with access limited to project members. Mailing lists are managed by OpenEdition through a system based on Sympa² (an open source mailing list manager). Public outputs and datasets related to the ontology will be made available through platforms such as Zenodo, GitLab or the project website, using persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) and standard access protocols such as HTTPS, REST APIs or OAI-PMH, where applicable. Metadata records will be indexed and retrievable through standard repository interfaces. Some datasets (e.g., interview recordings) remain proprietary and will only be made available after anonymisation or under explicit access conditions.
- **Interoperable:** The project ensures interoperability through the use of common file formats such as .csv, .txt, and .pdf. Data created in proprietary environments (e.g., Miro boards) are either exported in open formats or accompanied by descriptive metadata. This approach facilitates compatibility across analysis tools and platforms.
- **Reusable:** Anonymised and well-documented data will be made reusable through standardised metadata and documentation practices. For example, survey results from WP5 are anonymised and formatted to support reuse in future co-design studies, subject to explicit user consent where required. Where applicable, data outputs will be shared under open licenses, such as

² <https://www.sympa.community/>

Creative Commons licenses (e.g., CC BY) for public reports, deliverables, and structured knowledge resources like D2.1 (Ontology). This ensures transparency, reproducibility, and the possibility for third parties to build upon project outputs. Software developed within the project—including AI modules, data processing pipelines, and the LLM4SSH components—will be released under Open Source licenses, such as MIT, Apache 2.0, or GPL, depending on the component’s nature, compatibility, and intended level of openness. This includes codebases for enrichment pipelines, model training scripts, and reusable infrastructure tools. Any ethical or legal restrictions that apply to specific datasets will be clearly documented. In such cases, access conditions and reusability limitations will be transparently communicated to ensure responsible use while maximising the value of reusable outputs across the SSH and AI research communities.

The FAIR strategy is applied dynamically across the project's lifecycle, ensuring that evolving data types and sources remain compliant with these foundational principles.

4. Allocation of Resources

Data management responsibilities are distributed across WPs, with each Task Leader ensuring proper documentation, secure storage, and appropriate access control for the datasets under their responsibility. Each task includes allocated resources to support key data-related activities such as anonymisation, curation, metadata generation, and internal reporting.

WP1, and specifically Tasks T1.1 to T1.3, serve a coordinating role by overseeing the implementation of data governance procedures. These tasks include setting up internal data repositories (e.g., Google Drive structure), ensuring compliance with FAIR principles, and providing guidance on ethical handling of personal data collected through interviews and co-design workshops.

In addition, WP5 - and specifically Task 5.1 - develops legal and ethical guidelines that inform all aspects of data processing throughout the project. This includes the formulation of a Data Trust Framework covering privacy, access and data management. These efforts are aligned with relevant EU legislation, such as GDPR, European Data Governance Act³, Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI⁴ and the EU AI Act, and provide a common reference to data sharing, consent and accountability. WP1 ensures integration of these principles with practical data workflows and resource planning.

Resource allocation also includes:

- **Technical infrastructure:** Secure cloud storage (Google Drive) is provisioned and maintained centrally.
- **Human resources:** WP leaders and designated data stewards are responsible for metadata creation and DMP updates.
- **Budget allocation:** Specific line items in task budgets (e.g., in WP5 for interview transcription and survey analysis, in WP2 for ontology documentation and dissemination) cover data preparation and processing needs.

³ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance (Data Governance Act). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/868/oj>

⁴ High-Level Expert Group on AI. (2019). Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, European Commission, Brussels. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

In addition, certain tasks such as T2.1 and T5.3 involve outputs intended for public sharing (e.g., ontology datasets, user evaluation results), and include budgetary and technical support for open access publishing and archiving (e.g., on Zenodo). WP1 ensures alignment of these activities with the overall data strategy and regulatory compliance, including periodic review and revision of this DMP.

5. Data Security

Throughout the project, data will be securely stored using a dedicated cloud space (Google Drive) configured specifically for project-related work. Access to this space is strictly limited to authorised team members and controlled through Google Workspace's security mechanisms. Google Drive provides encryption during both transfer and storage, providing a secure environment for data. The platform also enables file versioning and change tracking to support data recovery when needed.

In the rare cases where local storage is necessary, it is limited to non-sensitive data only, unless there is no viable alternative. In such situations, local storage must be on encrypted disks with up-to-date antivirus protection, and access must be protected by strong passwords. Sensitive or personal data - such as survey results - must be anonymised at the earliest possible stage of processing and stored only in password-protected, encrypted GDPR-compliant environments.

All team members are instructed to follow best practices in data processing, including secure file transmission, regular password updates, and compliance with institutional and EU data protection regulations. Access rights are granted based on roles and responsibilities, periodically reviewed and revoked when no longer needed.

Programming code developed within the project is stored in a GitLab repository. Only designated developers responsible for software development are granted editorial access. GitLab provides secure storage, user access control and detailed change tracking to ensure traceability and accountability.

Regular backups of critical data are maintained via a cloud-based platform to minimise the risk of accidental loss.

6. Ethical Aspects

Throughout the life of the GRAPHIA project, all partners involved are required to maintain the highest ethical standards in all aspects of data collection, processing, storage and dissemination. Ethical issues are integrated into the project's data management procedures from the very beginning and are constantly reviewed.

Informed Consent

All participants taking part in qualitative research, such as interviews and workshops, are fully informed of the nature and purpose of the project, the intended use of their data, and their rights as participants. Consent is obtained prior to participation, usually through the submission of appropriate statements to be accepted. Participants are informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without any negative consequences.

Anonymisation

To protect the privacy and confidentiality of individuals, all sensitive or personally identifiable information is removed from datasets before analysis, processing or dissemination. This includes direct identifiers (e.g., names, email addresses) and indirect identifiers that may lead to re-identification in combination with other data (e.g., job titles, locations, affiliations).

Anonymisation is carried out in accordance with established best practices and in full compliance with the GDPR, using methods appropriate to the type of data. For textual data, this may include redaction or semantic masking; for audio or video recordings, voice distortion or transcription anonymisation may be used. Where full anonymisation is technically or contextually impossible - especially in qualitative research - pseudonymisation and strict access control mechanisms are implemented instead. All anonymisation and access control procedures are documented at the task level and periodically reviewed.

Responsible Use of AI Tools

In line with the project's use of artificial intelligence-based tools for data extraction, classification and enrichment, special attention has been paid to the ethical challenges associated with automated systems. These include the risk of factual inaccuracies (so-called "hallucinations"), propagation of social or algorithmic biases, and unintended reintegration of personal data. These concerns are addressed

through the ethical and legal framework developed in Task 5.1, which draws on the European Data Governance Act and the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI and applies the JUST principles (Judicious, Unbiased, Safe, Transparent) to guide responsible design and data handling.

Output generated by artificial intelligence systems will be critically reviewed by human experts before dissemination or reuse. Where enrichment pipelines involve external or pre-trained models, metadata will clearly distinguish between human- and machine-generated content. Efforts are being made to trace the origin of models, document uncertainty and ensure compliance with relevant ethical principles, including fairness, non-discrimination and respect for privacy.

Limited dissemination

All datasets intended for dissemination undergo thorough ethical and legal review to ensure that they do not contain personally identifiable or otherwise sensitive information.

Selected datasets - such as qualitative research results (e.g., transcriptions or recordings of interviews), stakeholder feedback and annotations generated by artificial intelligence - may remain restricted and will be shared only within the project consortium or under controlled access conditions. Access to such datasets may require specific agreements, such as signed declarations of data use or institutional consents, and is subject to the principles of proportionality, necessity and informed consent.

For public dissemination, documentation and metadata will clearly indicate any restrictions or limitations on use. Ethical and legal justifications for non-disclosure will be recorded and periodically reviewed to ensure ongoing compliance with FAIR principles and data management obligations.

Appendix A.

This appendix presents a preliminary data inventory table developed in the early stages of the GRAPHIA project as part of the preparation of this Data Management Plan. The table serves as a structured overview of the anticipated datasets across all work packages, including their origin, format, ownership, expected volume, level of access and sensitivity.

The list was developed through a coordinated consultation process with work package leaders and task owners, who provided input on the types of data they expect to generate, collect or reuse. It reflects an initial understanding of the project's data landscape and builds on early planning and design documents.

Given that the GRAPHIA project is still in its early stages, many of the items in this table are provisional or indicative. Specific details - such as exact data formats, licensing schemes and publication dates - will be refined as the project progresses and data collection activities develop. As such, the list should be viewed as a living, evolving component of the DMP, adapted to the dynamic nature of research workflows in large, interdisciplinary projects.

The table will be regularly reviewed and updated in future versions of the DMP, ensuring that it remains accurate, complete and aligned with the project's technical and ethical obligations.

A file to download ([GRAPHIA_Data_identification.xlsx](#)) will be made available in Zenodo together with this document.